

CHANGES IN THE FIELD OF MODERN ARCHITECTURE AND URBAN PLANNING IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article covers the reforms carried out in the field of architecture and construction in New Uzbekistan and their results, as well as the construction of various modern buildings built in the republic with the participation of foreign companies, and the reforms carried out in the development of the sector in the republic.

Keywords: Architecture, construction, infrastructure, construction quality, hotels, sports complexes, Tashkent City, banks, foreign cooperation.

In recent years, the construction sector in our country has been identified as an important priority sector of the national economy, demonstrating high growth rates due to the rapid reforms implemented in recent years.

The Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017–2021, adopted at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, and the State Programs adopted in accordance with it, place special emphasis on the construction sector as the locomotive of the economy in further accelerating the development of the country's economy, in particular the construction of new buildings and structures, new production facilities, as well as private entrepreneurship, railways and highways, and residential buildings.[1]

In particular, within the framework of this general strategy and the programs adopted in accordance with it, over the past 5 years, consistent reforms have been implemented to further improve the construction industry, form mechanisms for the consistent development of construction bodies and institutions, ensure the efficiency of the public administration system, and introduce digital technologies into the sector.

In 2018, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically improve the public administration system in the construction sector" was adopted. In accordance with the Decree, the Ministry of Construction was established on the basis of the State Committee for Architecture and Construction.

Also, on the basis of the Fund for Development and Material Promotion under the State Architecture and Construction Committee and the Fund for the Support of Educational Institutions, the Fund for the Support of the Ministry of

Construction and the Republican Center for Standardization and Certification in Construction was reorganized as the Republican Center for Standardization in Construction.

In turn, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Approval of the Urban Planning Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted in a new edition. The Code introduced "unique and particularly important objects", "advertising and information objects", "residential objects", "urbanization" and a number of other basic concepts, and defined the main principles of urban planning activities.

Also, the norms on public control in the field of urban planning activities and its forms and subjects were strengthened. It was also determined that public control should be involved in the discussion of decisions in this area.

It should be noted that 123 urban planning documents have been submitted for public discussion, and 109 of them have been discussed. Also, the "Geoportal" information system was created within the framework of the "Transparent construction" national information portal system to give the status of a public document to the master plans of settlements. General plans of 213 cities and towns in the country, architectural planning organization projects of 595 areas, detailed planning projects of 16 areas, and a total of 824 urban planning documents have been placed on Geoportal.[2]

The "Aware Citizen" system, which allows citizens to independently obtain information about objects under construction, identify illegal construction, record violations at construction sites and send them to the authorized bodies for construction control, has been launched in test mode.

Also, from March 1, 2021, a procedure has been introduced for the construction and reconstruction of buildings and structures with a height of more than two floors, a height of 12 meters above the ground and a total area of more than 500 square meters, including individual houses, subject to mandatory examination of the design documentation of the object and the implementation of state construction control by the territorial construction control inspectorates under the Ministry of Construction.

The scale of modern construction and urban development work carried out in Uzbekistan over the past five years is an unprecedented example of creativity in the fourth decade of our independence.

The expansion of affordable housing construction by the state, the implementation of a new mortgage program for the population in the regions, the "My First Home" project, and the construction of housing on the most favorable terms for young families in need of housing, the creation of towns in

regional centers with modern amenities and meeting international standards, and the commissioning of the third line of the modern underground metro in our capital, Tashkent, in order to solve existing problems with public transport, have become part of the history of New Uzbekistan.

The initiative of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev to introduce new articles on the right of the population to a decent life and housing in our Constitution in his Address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan on December 22, 2022, provided the legal basis for Uzbekistan to take a step towards a social state.

While the total volume of housing construction in Uzbekistan by 2021 amounted to 45,000 units, in the Address the President instructed to increase the volume of construction of new housing for the population by 1.5 times starting from 2023. In accordance with this instruction, as of 2024, about 20,000 houses have been built for the population in our country.[3]

In the past, when a compact town was built within a large city, it was usually called a “New City.” Times have changed, and terms such as modern architecture and urbanization have emerged. Human nature has become more sophisticated.

Not only in the world, but also in our country, new projects, construction methods, and new approaches are emerging in the construction of new cities. “London City,” “Moscow City,” “Ankara City,” and “Baku City,” which are known to the entire world, are among them. Now, in the capital of Uzbekistan, a town called “Tashkent City” has been built that fully meets the requirements of modern architecture and urban planning.

It is worth noting that the Tashkent City project was implemented mainly at the expense of private investors, and the initial concept of the business center was prepared by the world-famous British firm ARUP. The proposals of experienced seismologists from Uzbekistan, as well as experienced seismologists, scientists, and specialists from the United States, Japan, and Russia, who have conducted many years of testing in this field and have accumulated extensive experience, were taken into account in the earthquake resistance and seismicity of 45-50-story buildings in the center of the capital.

395 thousand square meters of housing, 281 thousand offices, 349 thousand retail spaces, and 64 thousand square meters of hotel rooms were built on the territory of the Tashkent City complex. 36 thousand square meters of area were prepared for conference and exhibition halls, and 9 thousand

square meters for educational institutions. Today, this complex has become one of the most attractive places in our capital.

In terms of metro construction, Uzbek builders have also achieved significant results in recent years. The underground and above-ground metro lines in our capital have been connected and turned into a ring. The second stage of metro construction began in 2022, and to date, a 12-kilometer overpass and 7 stations have been built, serving more than 40 thousand passengers per day.

To date, the total length of the Tashkent metro has exceeded 70 kilometers. Of this, 38 kilometers were built after 1977, while 32 kilometers of metro lines have been built in the last 7 years. The number of stations has reached 50. The number of daily passengers traveling by metro today exceeds one million. This is an important factor in reducing the need for personal transport among the population, and ultimately traffic jams on the streets.

Based on the analysis, according to the statistics agency, construction work worth 52.1 trillion soums was completed in Uzbekistan in 2023. According to the results of the last 9 months of 2024, the number of enterprises and organizations engaged in construction activities in our republic has reached 31,703. In conclusion, it can be said that today, under the initiative and leadership of our President, reforms are being carried out in our country to develop the construction sector, build exemplary housing for the population, and improve and beautify the territories of our beautiful country.

As a result, the scale of construction in our country is expanding year by year, and a long-term, urbanization process is being implemented in the regions. Construction work is also continuing at a rapid pace in rural areas. Of course, this requires improving the sector, ensuring transparency, and developing international cooperation. Because the highest goal of the reforms being carried out in the sector is, in the words of our esteemed President, to please our people and advance our beloved Motherland in all areas, turning it into a prosperous place.

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